

The Pronunciation Problems among Kurdish Learners of English

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Abstract:

The goal of this study was to examine the pronunciation issues of different speakers of English and especially Kurdish speakers, and various perspectives on native vs non-native speakers. The research showed that Kurdish speakers had difficulties pronouncing several English vowels and some English consonants. The research results demonstrate that Kurdish English speakers understand the value of pronunciation compared to native and non-native English speakers. Kurdish speakers may hesitate to speak in a manner that seems natural to a native speaker, and their last consonants in words are almost always unaspirated and unvoiced. Given that Kurdish learners of English have difficulty pronouncing some English words, some suggested solutions include providing pronunciation

instruction classes to language instructors, having educators speak in English, and giving students examples of native tongue sounds compared and contrasted with the target language sounds. With minimal exposure to cooperation with native speakers and variations in L1's phonological organization compared to English, the difficulty posed by pronunciation is evident. All the updated studies clearly show that these issues affect English speakers in general and rely less and less on their original tongue.

Keywords: *Pronunciation, Kurdish phonology, English phonetic, Problems, none native.*

Introduction

According to Hakim (2012), "no two people speak exactly alike. We can always hear differences between them - and the pronunciation of English varies a great deal in different geographical areas". Nowadays, many non-native speakers fear their pronunciation and feel embarrassed to speak in front of native speakers. Hassan (2012) states that good pronunciation is very helpful for understanding between native and non-native speakers;

however, even if speakers know perfect grammar and vocabulary, they cannot express their message; without good pronunciation, everything becomes meaningless. A person's behavior toward someone or something demonstrates their attitude, which may be good or bad, depending on how they or think and feel about that person or object (Pearson, 1983).

Generally, it can be seen that pronunciation problems occur to all non-native speakers (NNS) of different languages in the world, and the same problem exists in the pronunciation of

most of the Kurdish learners of English, which has become a common problematic strategy in this era.

Plenty of people have a strong desire to learn the English language with the correct pronunciation. Kurdish learners, another group of NNS of the English language, are not taught how to pronounce in their target language in such a way that native speakers of English can easily understand what they are saying during conversations and debates. Kurdish and English have peak syllabic systems, meaning each language has an equal number of syllables and vowels. Syllables in Kurdish are pronounced incorrectly in English sounds. For instance, they mispronounced the words (think and that) instead, they read the terms think as /θɪŋk/ and that as /ðat/ they expressed like this / sink/ and /zat/. So this issue belongs to that Kurdish alphabets do not exist with these two sounds, /ð/ and / θ/. Therefore, Kurdish permits consonant clusters with three sounds afterward but only two at the beginning of words. It also demonstrates that a syllable must include both a consonant and a vowel to be considered complete (Karimi, 1996). Not only native Kurdish speakers are confronted with this problem, but other languages native speakers have similar matters to deal with. Many researchers have shown that the errors made by speakers of other languages are something of a systematic origin more than an accidental one. Homdan and Moosa (1984) claimed that some sounds of the English language were substituted by Arab students who faced problems producing those sounds which were not known in their native languages, for instance, /v/ and /P/, because these two sounds do not exist in the Arabic language. Also, other nations, like Chinese speakers, make mistakes when pronouncing sounds different in English, like /sh/ and /r/, and are problematic and varied compared to Chinese sounds. Mohammed Claims (2011) Claims that speaking a foreign language with a mother tongue accent is neither strange nor unique. It is a characteristic that is distinctive of speakers from certain geographic origins, he continues. This is evident when one considers that even certain native English

speakers, such as Americans, Scots, and Irish, speak with their native accents.

Kurdish learners of English face some problems when speaking English because of their first language phonemic system, and the problem is producing sounds that do not have a similar sound in English. Some phonemes and phonological rules of the English language are quite different from the Kurdish phonological system, so these differences complicate the learning process for English learners. When Kurdish people learn English, they may pronounce /v/ as /w/, leading to mispronouncing words and phrases such as very and vest as /weri/ and /west/, respectively. Most northern dialect /v/ nouns are pronounced as /w/ in Sorani Kurdish (Nabaz, 1976).

The investigation and comparison of Kurdish and English phonologies are the main objectives of this work. The learners can distinguish between Kurdish and English phonological features and identify pronunciation issues by contrasting these features.

The present study is significant as a research project in several ways. First, the study shows the reflection of EFL learners toward pronunciation used in different situations. Second, it will show the effectiveness of some teaching techniques to improve speaking skills, as speaking is a primary focus that every EFL learner aims for.

The current study will attempt to answer the following questions:

1. How do Kurdish learners transfer phonological elements of their native language to the target English language?
2. What difficulties do teachers face while teaching English pronunciation to learners?

Literature Review

Numerous research is being conducted to understand L2 pronunciation better. A distinct facet of accent is the focus of each analysis. Studies on attitudes toward articulation are included in some, while investigations into the

causes of pronunciation problems are covered in others. In the beginning, research focusing on mistakes made by Kurdish speakers will be presented. The authors will also review the research addressing more broad issues faced by English language learners whose first language is not Kurdish. These studies are included to illustrate some general problems connected with this study.

Keshavarz (2001) investigated to make an investigation among Persian learners of English that have some issues with the pronunciation of initial consonant clusters because the Persian language does not allow initial consonant clusters. The data were gathered by asking the participants to read some materials and through a test that included 30 female and male participants from an institute in Mashhad. Their ages were between 18-30 years old. The findings indicated that the students' speaking difficulties were caused by their usage of their mother tongues, a lack of competency, and their inability to cope with the complicated initial consonant clusters that differed so much according to their phonological understanding.

Barros (2003) carried out a study on ESL Arab learners in Saudi Arabia that has pronunciation difficulties with English consonants. The researcher collected the data via two research instruments – a word list and a reading passage the participants had to read aloud. The results of the study indicated how three sounds were pronounced. The study analyzed the complexity and patterns of pronunciation of the voiceless /p/ bilabial stop, the alveolar approximate /r/, and the voiced /v/ labiodental fricative. Six Arabic speakers were involved in the research, and they mispronounced these sounds, although they have been living in the United States of America for four years.

O'Connor and Yule (2003) investigated the challenges of English pronunciation among Sudanese students who spoke Arabic. The results show they have problems pronouncing sounds such as /z/, /p/, and /s/. The influence of their mother tongue was evident in the pronunciation of the English language. This study's data were collected using questionnaires,

tape recordings, tests, and reading a passage aloud. The research included 50 students (first stage) of SUST at the education college. The results of this research show that when Sudanese students of English say or read some materials in English, most of them make mistakes in pronouncing the consonant mentioned above.

Al-Saidat (2010) studied the phonological analysis of Arabic speakers learning English in Jordan. By doing phonological analyses of the participants' English as a second language, the research sought to identify the types of pronunciation issues that participants faced. Along with examining the causes of these processes, it also discussed the various de-clusterization techniques utilized by the participant's interlanguages. Twenty Jordanian students who were English majors at two state-funded colleges were included in this study. He recorded the group's actions while they browsed a random word list using computers. According to the study's results, Arab English learners struggle to acquire certain English syllables.

The research was carried out by Hakim (2012) on undergraduate Java students enrolled in an English study program to investigate how Java students pronounce English sounds such as /b/, /d/, /g/, /j/, /dz/ and /ð/ in English. The findings revealed that two of six sounds are challenging for Java undergraduate students to articulate. These two sounds are /d/ and /ð/, respectively.

Chan (2009) stated, "does mother tongue influence have a greater effect on L2 speech perception or production?" Perception plays a crucial part in learning English speech in helping students comprehend the sound, and creating the sound is advantageous for practice. The researcher considered that Cantonese individuals find it difficult to pronounce English consonants, such as /v/ and /f/, despite how easily they can hear them. They were English majors from three regional universities who had been thinking about the dialect for at least a decade. The results demonstrated that Cantonese ESL students in Hong Kong had more trouble establishing L2 sounds that do not exist in the L1 phonological framework than L1

and L2 sounds. However, the findings of this study demonstrated that there is a distinct way in which learners perceive English discourse sounds because the absence of L2 sounds in L1 does not always result in problems with discernment, and the presence of a sound in both L1 and L2 phonemic inventories does not necessarily help with recognition.

According to Isa (2011), Nigeria is a diverse nation where many people speak various indigenous languages. They express these languages as their mother tongues.

Pal (2013) researched how the mother tongue impacts spoken English. The study investigates Indian students who are from a government school. The results show many speakers of Hindi learners have problems in the case of pronunciation challenges, especially in these areas which are seen: one of the obstacles is affricative sounds such as /s/, /ʃ/, /z/, /ʒ/ and /dʒ/, English consonant clusters, English vowel sounds that are distinct from Hindi sounds, and pluralization/plural indicators. Furthermore, the spelling is different.

Furthermore, Nkamigbo (2010) used a sample of the Igbo dialect to undertake a phonological study on teacher preparation in Nigeria. The result demonstrates that certain sound segments are present in different Igbo dialects but are absent from standard Igbo; they join/ð/ additionally, /θ/ consonants, and voiced and voiceless dental fricatives separately. As a result, dialect teachers should be selected from the regions whose dialects develop troublesome sound components and should be incorporated into a school's curriculum. The investigation results indicate that only the Ika dialect of Igbo possesses intonation. Thus if you want to teach other people your dialect, you need to choose a dialect teacher from a location where their dialect has secure intonation.

Ducate and Lomicka (2009) conducted a study on English syllabic consonants and quality factors in educated Yoruba Nigerian English. The researcher finds out that Yoruba-taught Syllabic consonants are seldom used as syllable peaks by English speakers since Standard English is the language that governs them.

Instead, they add strong vowels in between the consonants that came before and the alleged syllabic consonant. As an example, the word "pebble" (/pebl/), which was founded as /pebu/, serves as the replacement.

Sedlackova (2007) studied a few elements of Portuguese speakers' learning of non-native English pronunciation. The study's researcher revealed that Portuguese speakers of English struggled to pronounce the /h/ sound, determining whether it should be silent or not in a word. They also had trouble pronouncing long vowels. Thus, they would often replace them with the nearest vowel in their language. They also had problems with the sounds /b/ and /g/ that they shifted since these two sounds are absent from their L1 linguistic structure.

Additionally, Sultangubiyeva, Avakova and Kabdrakhmanova (2013) discovered that Kazakh pupils struggle to acquire the English /a:/ sound in their research on learning English pronunciation compared to Kazakh. They alter the long vowel (found in words like "star" and "garden") both qualitatively and quantitatively. According to the study's findings, to minimize the impact of students' native languages on their pronunciation of the sound in question, teachers need to make an effort to reduce the effects of students' native languages on their pronunciation of the sound in question with their students.

Alharbi (2009) investigated the difficulties faced by Saudi learners in pronouncing the English voiceless bilabial /p/as the word (shop) in the three different positions (initial, medial, and final); this was the aim of the study. In this study, twenty participants in, both female and male ESL students, were chosen. After the study concluded, the data were gathered using a questionnaire and read a list of 20 words in the abovementioned position. It was seen that there were seven kinds of errors which they have done since they did not have such a sound as /p/ in their language, which is why they replaced /p/ with /b/ in the case of approximation and friction.

Varol (2012) investigated the impact of Turkish phonology on English loanwords from Indo-

Europe. According to this study, Turkish adults have difficulty articulating the English sounds, θ , δ , \mathfrak{r} , and \mathfrak{t} , which are not present in their first language.

Research on the influence of regional dialects on the development of English sound production by Japanese language students was conducted by Bada (2001). The specialist used a total of 18 individuals. There were a total of sixteen females, while there were only two males present. Their ages ranged from 18 to 29, with 19 years as the group's mean age. The findings support the hypothesis that Japanese students of English have difficulty retaining the unvoiced form of the English /d/ sound. Similar challenges are associated with the sound /z/ when it appears at the end location of a word among Japanese English learners. This occurs when the /s/spelling character displays the phoneme/z/as in "possession," strained checking, and pluralization. The actual issue with English sounds for Japanese English learners has to do with both / θ /and / δ / sounds. Japanese English learners are having trouble with the phonemes /v/ and /f/ since they are borrowed words from Western languages and are represented in Hiragana script via freshly created visuals. They also have trouble with the sounds /l/ and /r/. They mispronounced /r/ as /l/ when it should have been the other way around. Only Japanese female pupils could articulate the sound /s/ for /f/.

Another study was done by Syananondh (1983). He researched Thia speakers of English to find out their pronunciation challenges. The data were gathered through a questionnaire that was given to them, and the study included three hundred students who graduated from colleges and universities in the united states a long time; the result showed that 212 of them answered the questionnaires and The researcher identified one student as having trouble comprehending spoken English in various communication contexts when they initially arrived in the United States. Therefore, it can be seen that two different English pronunciations were taught in Thailand. These things which were happened because of inadequate English vocabulary, lack of English conversation, and also it can be seen

that their complexity of English listening comprehension. Consonant sounds might be considered the sturdy building bricks from which we build words, phrases, and sentences. The vowels of the language serve as the links or glue holding these pieces together (Celce-Murcia et al., 1996).

Similar research was done on the perceptual distortions that Korean speakers experience while adapting English consonant clusters by Kabak and Idsardi (2007). The study aimed to demonstrate that contact violations would alter perceptually if any illegal consonant sequence caused perceptual epenthesis. Additionally, they attempted to illuminate the cause of perceptual illusions. The research's conclusions demonstrated that syllable structural limits, not consonantal contact restrictions, were to blame for the impression of epenthesis in L2 and the induction of perceptual epenthesis. Furthermore, it was shown that the voice was depicted as dangling in Korean listeners' perceptions. The findings also showed that Korean listeners did not use several phonological phenomena, such as neutralization, lateralization, and nasalization processes, to correct and change misplaced consonant sequences. Also, according to a contrastive analysis study conducted by Vidovic (1972). In order to anticipate the pronunciation challenges faced by both English and Serbo-Croatian language learners, he compared the two sound systems. He used terms with the same sounds in both languages for the comparison and asked native speakers who had not heard the words to pronounce them. He requested a native English speaker to pronounce the Serbo-Croatian word *sit*, which means "filled up," and native Serbo-Croatian speakers to pronounce the English word *sit* like /st/. The discrepancies between each sound were then examined and reported.

Moreover, a survey-based study was carried out by Nowacka (2012) about the views of EFL university learners in three European countries: Italy, Poland, and Spain. The findings showed that learners believe it is critical to possess good pronunciation and hope to sound native-like; their pronunciation progressed by appreciating "listening to authentic English, practical

phonetics instruction, imitating authentic speech as well as through contacts with native speakers" (Nowacka, 2012) and that they planned to work on their pronunciation by reading aloud, imitating authentic speeches from various media, listening to or watching programs, drilling and employing materials such as books, tapes, and dictionaries.

Lindsay (2000) researched teachers from Bangladesh's public and private universities. The data were gathered through a questionnaire for teachers that consisted of eight multiple-choice questions. The study included fifty-one teachers who contributed as an instructor in the department of engineering and technology. The result of the research showed that each of the eight questions had a different result. For instance: the first question was, "Are teachers satisfied with the students' pronunciation level while they use it in English language classes?" Only 80% of teachers answered the option satisfied, while 60% replied dissatisfied with the student's pronunciation. Similar results can be seen in other questions, but the last one has a different consequence, asking teachers, "Do your students improve their pronunciation at the end of the course?"

Most of the teachers who rated 64 % responded yes they do, while 34% replied with the option "no they do not". In Izmir, Bekleyen (2011) conducted a study about pronunciation challenges which makes complexity in many aspects for Turkish learners of English. The data were collected through oral practices; the study included 24 participants who were tested by using read-aloud and open-ended questions. The findings of this study showed the result occurred in many places of the sounds of English that confused them while they were using them, such as the sound Schwa (ə), voiced and voiceless Th (/ð/-/θ/) and (/ŋ/). This study was conducted at the university of Gediz.

Peterson (2000) conducted one research on acquiring pronunciation. In a study titled "Pronunciation Learning Strategies: A First Look," Peterson examined a few studying techniques used by adult Spanish learners who were learning the language as a second language

to correct communication problems and enhance their pronunciation. In the research described above, he looked into the pronunciation acquisition techniques employed by English speakers learning Spanish as a second language. Eleven students from Spanish classrooms at The Ohio State University participated, and they were at three distinct levels (beginning, intermediate, and advanced). Using interviews and the diaries kept by these eleven adult learners, the researcher in this study looked at twelve tactics. The study's findings demonstrated the importance of pronunciation and language learning techniques for effective language acquisition and the necessity for empirical research in these areas.

Pilot research was conducted by Vitanova and Miller (2002) to determine the relationship between motivation and pronunciation practice. 100 adults who were college-level participants were utilized in the research. Graduate ESL students who had learnt different pronunciation techniques independently without a teacher's guidance made up the participants. The investigation did not provide the exact number of participants. In this study, the researchers examined the pronunciation teaching methodologies and elements the students valued the most. The researchers believed that if learners were given pronunciation skills, they would continue to advance outside the classroom. The researchers discovered that ESL graduate students had favourable feedback on the empowerment of self-monitoring, self-correction, and autonomous learning techniques after using open-ended prompts to elicit their perspectives on learning pronunciation. Students understood the need for training in metacognitive strategies other words.

Eckstein (2007) investigated the link between 183 adult ESL Brigham Young University learners' spontaneous pronunciation performance and their pronunciation learning methodologies. The researcher's goal in this study was to evaluate the relationship between adult ESL learners' pronunciation learning methodologies and their spontaneous pronunciation competence. He also investigated the strategic learning of pronunciation using

pronunciation learning methodologies tied to pronunciation acquisition theory. He used strategic pronunciation learning surveys and a standardized speaking level accomplishment exam for data gathering. This research demonstrated that rapid self-correction and asking for assistance were the most effective. Symbol systems and one's original sound system were the least desired pronunciation enhancement techniques, but they were the most commonly employed ones.

The last research was presented by Akyol (2012) and titled "Instruction in English Pronunciation Goals and Priorities an investigation of Turkish EFL learners' pronunciation learning techniques." 82 Turkish university students were taking the English course. The major goals were to examine the different learning techniques new EFL instructors at the English Language Teaching Department used to enhance English pronunciation. For data collection, the researcher employed a questionnaire on pronunciation methods based on taxonomies of pronunciation learning strategies published by Oxford (1990) and Peterson (2000). This research suggested that using pronunciation learning strategies is essential to making pronunciation learning much more enjoyable, independent, and suited to satisfy the requirements of communicative-oriented classrooms.

Methodology

Two studies have been used in this research as the sources of data collection. The first is "Pronunciation Errors of Turkish Learners of English", conducted by Geylanioglu and Dikilitaş (2012). They used a mixed (qualitative and quantitative) method for collecting their data.

The second source is "Survey of Kurdish Students' Sound Segment and Syllabic Pattern Errors in the Course of Learning EFL", conducted by Mohammadi (2014). He used a survey as a method to collect the data.

The subjects in the research conducted by Geylanioglu and Dikilitaş (2012) in the study's

first phase were 24 Turkish students. They were randomly selected at the Gediz University in Izmir. Their levels began at the basic level and are presently pre-intermediate. They don't get any pronunciation training particularly. In productive classes, where students can speak and listen, and in receptive courses, where they hear the instructor communicate, they accidentally pick up the pronunciation. English must be studied diligently to become proficient enough to handle the course requirements for their degrees. Since students must engage in contentious conversation, speaking is a key curriculum component.

60 students were randomly selected for the study's second phase from the same environment and were given a questionnaire about their past activities for acquiring pronunciation. Although there are just a handful of Turkish learners, it is important to remember that this data may provide insight into how pronunciation development generally occurs.

On the other side, Jahangir recruited 50 pre-university students who were native Kurdish speakers to participate in his research, which he performed. In Kamyaran, a city in Kurdistan Province, the participants were randomly picked from two pre-university institutes. 25 students that participated were female, while the remaining 25 were male. In terms of their first-term English test, the topics were uniform. The volunteers for this research ranged from 18 to 20, and they all participated willingly and with curiosity.

Data collection procedures

Geylanioglu and Dikilitaş (2012) used 30 words with three distinct sound patterns (the 'th' sound in its voiceless /θ/ and voiced /ð / versions, the schwa/ə /, and the 'Ng' sound /ŋ /). These noises were the result of student mispronunciations that were recorded during the school year. The specific sounds that each mispronounced word included were used to classify them.

Two instruments were employed in this investigation. First, in a one-on-one session, the

students had to read the challenging words out one after the other while the instructor recorded their pronunciations. In order to observe the student pronunciations in proper form and compare them with typical sound patterns, the recordings were then converted into IPA. The list of pronunciations was then completed. The second tool was an open-ended questionnaire with a single question to help them understand how their instructors had previously taught them pronunciation. The comments were necessary since certain teaching methods may have contributed to pupils' pronunciation errors. The information was gathered retrospectively and in the form of written reports. The replies were believed to provide information regarding their pronunciation learning history and support the need for pronunciation instruction to be included at a conceptual level, especially via conceptualization. Three troublesome sounds were verbally evoked for this purpose, and one open-ended inquiry was posed to learn more about the participants' prior and present pronunciation expertise.

In the research done by Mohammadi (2014), On the other hand, the instrument employed in this study was a bound oral production test with several passages that the participants had to read out. Some of the quotes came from the first and second books of the Preparatory English Course. In contrast, others were taken from "Bridging the Gap," a book by the Educational Measurement and Evaluation Organization with a readability index ranging from 8.755 to 10.432, corresponding to the readability index of texts for pre-university. Each student was requested to read a few lines aloud while having his voice captured to document his pronunciation. After obtaining bound oral production samples, they were IPA phonologically transcribed. The participants' pronunciation was also recorded using the symbols "V" and "C" to denote vowels and consonants, respectively, to study the formation of syllabic patterns. Kavaliauskiene (2009) stated that "cross-linguistic similarities and differences can produce positive or negative transfer such as underproduction, overproduction, production errors, and misinterpretation".

In order to accomplish the research's main objective, the following actions were followed, which were done so since this study was conducted within the contexts of discourse analysis and defect detection:

First, the position and style of articulation and the sound clusters' combinatory strength were used to clearly define the English and Kurdish sound systems.

Second, the two languages under study's phonological segments and syllabic patterns were closely examined for contrastive analysis.

Third, it was discovered and expected that English phonological segments and syllabic patterns that do not exist in Kurdish would be problematic speech regions.

Fourth, an experiment involving 50 male and female pre-university students was conducted to verify the actual results instead of the expected ones. While their pronunciation was being captured, they read several paragraphs aloud. So samples of bound oral output were collected.

Fifth, the syllabic patterns created by the Kurdish pupils were represented using the symbols "V" and "C," and all of the vocal samples were phonemically transcribed in IPA.

Lastly, an inaccuracy analysis was carried out using the data that had been collected. A hierarchy of mistakes was produced by identifying, examining, and computing the phonological faults. The objective was to determine whether or not the contrastive analysis's results matched the predictions.

Discussion and Results

Analysis of Geylanioglu and Dikilitaş (2012) study

The initial research topic in the study by Geylanioglu and Dikilitaş (2012) was determining how students pronounce troublesome sounds. The nasal /ng/sound articulation had the highest accurate score (51%) out of the three phonemes recorded, demonstrating that the students were more adept at creating ng sounds than the other two

sounds, schwa /ə/ and the voiced and voiceless (/ð/(/θ/)) "th". Regarding the pronunciation of the schwa sound, it seems extremely unsuitable, particularly in light of the pupils' knowledge of the location of the schwa. By 16%, the pupils pronounced this sound properly. The schwa sound is represented in the schwa-containing words above by several vowel sounds, including (/a/, /e/, /i/, and /o/). This can make it harder for children to hear the schwa sound while pronouncing the term. Students also had difficulties with the sound since only 13% of complete word utterances were phonologically accurate.

Regarding the second query, "What may be the causes of these sounds being mispronounced?" An open-ended questionnaire was presented to help the students pinpoint the reasons behind their pronunciation errors. According to their quotes, the primary factors were connected to the instructors' instructional strategies. The lack of attention given to pronunciation instruction in the classroom was identified as one of the main reasons for word mispronunciation, according to the comments provided by the 60 participants.

The findings above support the notion that pronunciation instruction in language acquisition is neglected (Ahmadi, 2011; Bekleyen, 2011). As described in the students' retrospective descriptions, the instructors' methods may be responsible for their pupils' poor performance in pronouncing the words phonologically properly. The students in this research mispronounce even the terms with the highest frequency of content or function in the spoken and written English corpus. This demonstrates that pronunciation is severely neglected or directly seen as secondary in teaching foreign languages.

Analysis of Jahangir's (2014) study

In this study, the researcher investigated "A Survey of Kurdish Students' Sound Segment and Syllabic Pattern Errors in the Course of Learning EFL". Overall analysis revealed that the individuals made 754 pronunciation mistakes. Among the inaccuracies, 302 were brought on by the involvement of native tongue sound

segments, 209 by word spelling and pronunciation issues, 83 by the issue of silent letters, and 160 by discrepancies in syllable patterns between Kurdish and English. We may estimate that 462 mistakes, or 61.27 percent of all student pronunciation errors, were caused by influence from the student's native language (Kurdish).

Conclusion

Summarizing the study of Geylanioglu and Dikilitaş (2012), proper pronunciation is essential in language training and learning a new language. This affects the learners' level of competence when they use the target language in their daily lives, whether as a tool or a need. This is one of the most important reasons why it is important for language education courses to include teaching how to pronounce words properly. The modern teaching method of teaching second languages stresses the student's ability to speak the target language accurately and effectively. Therefore, in light of recent findings that place a greater emphasis on the acceptability of a language's pronunciation than on the speech intelligibility of that language, students of the language need to improve their levels of pronunciation to maximize the effectiveness of their communication in terms of L2 acquisition.

Furthermore, the nasal /ng/sound articulation had the highest accurate score (51%) out of the three phonemes recorded in this research, demonstrating that students were better able to produce ng sounds than the other two sounds, schwa /ə/ and the voiced and voiceless (/ð/(/θ/)) "th."

The participants of Jahangir's study (2014) together produced a total of 754 errors in pronunciation. The interference of mother tongue sound segments was responsible for 302 of the errors, word spelling, and pronunciation issues were responsible for 209 of the errors, silent letters were responsible for 83 of the errors, and differences between Kurdish and English syllable structures were responsible for 160 of the errors in syllabic structure. It is possible that the interference of the native

language, in this case, Kurdish, is to blame for an overall frequency of mistakes equal to 462 errors, which accounts for 61.27 per cent of all pupils' pronunciation difficulties.

The results of these two studies demonstrated the importance of English pronunciation. However, as the findings of the two secondary sources revealed, most English language learners struggle with pronunciation. Most of the mistakes they make are caused by the impact of their mother tongue. However, it is also important to consider the pupils' levels, ages, interests, and demands. The following suggestions were made based on the study's conclusion and results.

Students stated that they have difficulty acquiring pronunciation through reading and listening and more difficulties during speaking. Therefore, teachers need to develop ways to improve pronunciation through those teaching the four skills: listening, speaking, writing, and reading.

Since teachers support using the target language in teaching pronunciation, multi-word senses, and synonyms must be paid more attention to teachers who teach pronunciation. This can be done by discussing new words and expressions and providing them in many different ways.

The results showed that teachers have positive attitudes toward teaching pronunciation through their practices. So, pronunciation should be reflected as the main objective in teachers' course plans while studying English pronunciation rules to increase students' abilities in learning English.

References

- Akyol, T. (2012). A study on identifying pronunciation learning strategies of Turkish EFL learners. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 70(1), 1456-1462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.01.211>
- Alharbi, K. N. (2013). *Saudi learners' pronunciation difficulties with the English voiceless bilabial stop /p/*. Southern Illinois University Carbondale.
- Bada, E. (2001). Native language influence of the production of English sounds by Japanese learners. *The Reading Matrix*, 1(2), 1-15.
- Barros, A. (2003). *Pronunciation difficulties in the consonant system experienced by Arabic speakers when learning English after the age of puberty*. Unpublished MA Thesis. West Virginia University, WV.
- Bekleyen, N. (2011). Pronunciation Problems of the Turkish EFL Learners. *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*, 10(36), 94-107.
- Celce-Murcia, M., Brinton, D. M., & Goodwin, J. M. (1996). *Teaching pronunciation: A reference for teachers of English to speakers of other languages*. Cambridge University Press.
- Chan, A.Y. (2009). *Does mother tongue influence have a greater effect on L2 speech perception or production? A study of the learning of English by Cantonese ESL learners in Hong Kong*. UCL Psychology and Language Sciences. Retrieved from: www.ucl.ac.uk/psychlangsci/ptlc/proceedings_2009_CHAN_001_ed.
- Ducate, L. & Lomicka, L. (2009). Podcasting: an effective tool for honing language students' pronunciation? *Language Learning & Technology*, 13(3), 66-86.
- Eckstein, G. T. (2007). *A correlation of pronunciation learning strategies with spontaneous English pronunciation of adult ESL learners*. MA Thesis. Brigham Young University, UK.
- Hakim, R.A. (2012). An Analysis of Phonetics /b/, /d/, /g/, /j/, /dz/, and /ð/ into English Pronunciation for Java Students. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(20), 244-256.
- Homdan, A. H. (1984). *Utilizing the Theory of Articulatory Settings in the Teaching of English Pronunciation to Saudi Students Learning English as a Second Language*. Doctoral Dissertation, King Fahd Public Library.
- Isa, A. A. (2011). *The influence of mother tongue on the spoken English of some students: A case study of Government Girls' Secondary School*. Nguru, Yobe State, Nigeria.

- Karimi Doostan, G. H. (1996). The phonemic system of the Kurdish dialect of Sanandaj. *Linguistics*, 1(10), 55-62
- Kavaliauskiene, G. (2009). Role of mother tongue in learning English for specific purposes. *ESP word*, 1(22), 1-51.
- Keshavarz, M. H. (2001). *A practical course of English phonetics and phonology*. Tehran: Scientific and Cultural Publications Company.
- Lindsay, P. (2000). *Teaching English Worldwide*. California: Alta Book Center Publishers.
- Mohammadi, J. (2014). A survey of Kurdish students' sound segment & syllabic pattern errors in the course of learning EFL. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 5(3), 18-21.
- Mohammed, K.B. (2011). *Effects of mother tongue interference in second language acquisition: A case study of native Hausa learners of English language*. Dissertation submitted to the department of English and French, Bayero University. Kano Nigeria.
- Nabaz, J. (1976). *The Unified language of Kurdish*. (In Kurdish). Germany: The National Union of the Kurdish Students in Europe.
- Nkamigbo, L. C. (2010). Phonology in Teacher Education in Nigeria: The Igbo Language Example. *African Journal of Education*, 1(1), 48-63. <https://doi.org/10.21083/ajote.v1i1.1593>
- Nowacka, M. (2012). Questionnaire-based pronunciation studies: Italian, Spanish and Polish students' views on their English pronunciation. *Research in Language*, 10, 43-61. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10015-011-0048-3>
- Pal, S. (2013). Mother tongue influence on spoken English. Retrieved from: www.conference.pixelonline.net/ICT4LL2013/common/download/Paper_pdf/243RVS0FPiIC2013.pdf.
- Pearson, E. L. (1983) *Longman Active Study Dictionary*. Edinburgh Gate, England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Peterson, S.S. (2000). *Pronunciation Learning Strategies: A First Look*. Retrieved from: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Pronunciation-Learning-Strategies%3A-A-First-Look-Peterson/8069fbd5d78cb4c6820eab9e1cc56a8c8d05074>
- Sedlackova, K. (2007). *Some aspects of Non-native Acquisition of English Pronunciation in Portuguese Speakers*. Retrieved from: www.is.muni.cz/th/160409/pedf_b/Balakarska_prace.txt.
- Sultangubiyeva, A. Avakova, R. & Kabdrakhmanova, G. (2013). Learning English Pronunciation in Comparison with Kazakh Language. *American Journal of Linguistics*, 2(3), 33-36. doi: 10.5923/j.linguistics.20130203.01.
- Syananondh, K. (1983). *An Investigation of Pronunciation and Learning Strategies: Factors in English Listening Comprehension of Thai-Speaking Graduate Students in the United States*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Rutgers The State University of New Jersey. New Brunswick.
- Varol, M. (2012). *The influence of Turkish sound system on English pronunciation*. MA thesis. Florida State University, Tallahassee, FL.
- Vitanova, G. & Miller, A. (2002). Reflective practice in pronunciation learning. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 8(1).